

Unlocking Economic Growth: Empowering Local Industries through the One District, One Product Initiative and Export Expansion - A Case Study of Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract:- This Paper examines the role of the ‘One District One Product initiative’ in empowering local industries and export expansion in Uttar Pradesh. The One District, One Product (ODOP) initiative was developed and implemented by the Uttar Pradesh government as a novel way to revitalize and market the state's cultural legacy at the district level. After incorporating the evidence from literature reviews, government websites and reports, this study found that ODOP is a unique and highly successful initiative of the Government of Uttar Pradesh. In just two years, the success of the ODOP in Uttar Pradesh has inspired more than just other Indian states to undertake similar initiatives to revitalize local crafts and products at the National as well as global levels.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the oldest cultures in the world is the practice of handicrafts. Among the many handicrafts around the world, Indian Handicrafts Items go back to one of the oldest civilizations in the world, the Indus Valley Civilization.

Up until the arrival of the British, India's handicraft industry thrived during the medieval era and kept expanding. After the British and other colonial powers arrived in India, the handicrafts sector found it difficult to compete in the international market. The handicrafts sector relied solely on one's manual dexterity; therefore, producing something took time and effort. The price at which it was to be sold was, therefore, also high. However, because British goods produced by machines were less expensive, individuals soon started to turn to British goods.

The fact that the raw materials used to create different goods were drawn from nature hence they were not meant to last for a long time, is another factor in why the British took over the handicrafts industry. Therefore, the technique used to extend the lifespan of the produced goods was time-consuming and expensive.

This was mostly brought on by competition from British imports of machine-made items. Britain was able to flood the Indian markets with low-cost goods, especially

cotton textiles, thanks to its capacity for mass production. The railways made it easier to transport these commodities to India's most isolated regions and to buy raw materials there. These items created in large quantities posed a serious threat to the traditional handicraft industry.

The East India Company was able to set the terms of commerce thanks to its free trade policy. They forced Indian artisans to sell their wares below market value and employed them at wages that were lower than the going rate, among other things. They also forced artisans and laborers to produce agricultural output so that Company could export Raw Materials to Britain to support and fulfil their requirements during Industrialization and imports Machine made Finished goods in India with the main to demolish Indian handicrafts and treating India as Market place of for Industrial Output produced at the Industries of Britain.

After the Independence Era of India, the scenario was not so easy for Traditional Handicraft artisans; even in some cases Survival was the question because of the big social and Economic problems and lack of Government intervention and support. The situation became more adverse after major Economic Reforms in 1991 with the introduction of Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization. Indian Handicraft Industry has faced many problems and is not able to survive in front of modern machine art, which is comparatively very low in cost and with modern abstracts and art. Here with the introduction of schemes like One Product One District (ODOP), which provide all possible assistance and aid towards targeted Handicraft and Groups to make Art and Handicraft Products popular worldwide.

In a New India, diversity, a crucial characteristic of our country that is acknowledged throughout the world, is being further developed. The government has given this diversity, which can be found in a wide variety of dance styles, music, artwork, cuisine, and handicrafts, a top priority. To ensure that the millions of people who participate in local arts and crafts have sustainable livelihoods, the government has given the greatest importance to protecting, revitalizing, and popularising them.

A thorough approach was required right once to distinguish, **One District One Product (ODOP)**, safeguard and foster our traditional abilities in India's largest state as well, where food, textiles, dialects, dance forms, and art differ every few km.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The extraordinary success of the ODOP's regional economic revitalization plan in Uttar Pradesh has served as a model for the nation's other 27 states and 8 union territories. The three years since ODOP's introduction in Uttar Pradesh have yielded positive results, but its full potential has yet to be realized. Given the success and positive effects of the OVOP concept, it will be extremely helpful for the economic revival and inclusive development of those nations that are struggling with issues like income inequality, increasing pressure from rural-urban migration, dwindling local skills and crafts, and a lack of employment opportunities (**Tripathi & Agrawal, 2021**). Whereas in this paper author found that the training programs under ODOP need to be designed to the needs of the market so that they can put the training to use right away. When more workers from this sector participate in the handicraft industry, and money is made to raise the country's GDP, the Indian economy would benefit. The handicraft industry can produce jobs, improve workers' skills, and launch businesses locally to increase employment and help solve problems (**Uma Shankar Yadav, n.d., 2022**).

Natsuda (2012) Based on the experience of the One Village, One Product (OVOP) movement in Japan, this study examines the evolution of the One Tambon, One Product (OTOP) project in Thailand. It was originally designed in Japan as a strategy to stop rural population decline, but when it was applied in Thailand, the emphasis shifted to reducing poverty. It will be demonstrated how, despite some objections, the OTOP programme has given localities the chance to promote their products and generate employment prospects. The article covers an industrial case study as well as a small sample survey of the OTOP in the province of Chiang Mai.

Mahur (2022) According to this paper, this plan, a sizable number of people lack any kind of knowledge regarding it. And second, the rural areas' financial issues. First and foremost, this programme aims to disseminate information to both urban and rural residents, such as advertisements and posters, and to offer loans of any kind to help new businesses get off the ground or boost local economies. Every district has a tag to introduce itself, and this system is very important for the future or improving the economy of the district year after year. Every district now has a new digester thanks to this scheme.

Radiah (2009) This paper suggests continuous aid and a favourable environment provided by Government excel the small entrepreneurs in rural areas.

III. ONE DISTRICT ONE PRODUCT (ODOP) INITIATIVE IN UTTAR PRADESH

The One District, One Product (ODOP) initiative was developed and implemented by the Uttar Pradesh government as a novel way to revitalize and market the state's cultural legacy at the district level. This program has had a profound impact since it was introduced in 2018, not only reviving the state's traditional crafts that are at risk of extinction from the district level in Uttar Pradesh but also securing the livelihoods of millions of rural residents who participate in these activities. The scheme's execution in Uttar Pradesh has increased the state's export capacity by more than 30% since the program's debut in 2018. This is in addition to creating jobs and stable incomes for numerous underprivileged people, primarily craftsmen and artisans involved in the creation of traditional goods. In just two years, the ODOP's success in Uttar Pradesh has encouraged numerous other Indian states to implement comparable programs to encourage entrepreneurship nationwide and revive local crafts and products at the district level. It aims to turn every district in the nation into a world-class hub with the ability to produce, sell, and export a district's specialty product at every stage of the value chain. In light of Prime Minister Narendra Modi's trailblazing "Atama Nirbhar Bharat Abhiyan" program, which aims to promote domestic businesses and make India self-sufficient, ODOP gains even more significance and relevance. The goal of the state government was to choose one distinctive product from each of Uttar Pradesh's 75 districts and establish a traditional industrial centre for that particular product (ODOP UP, (Nayyar, 2021)).

A. Key Objectives of ODOP Initiatives:

The ODOP has been a game-changing step in realizing a district's true potential, helping to drive economic growth, create jobs, and encourage rural entrepreneurship; emphasis is still placed on creating an enabling ecosystem and offering assistance schemes for a single commodity, including manufacturing infrastructure. Here are a few key objectives for the ODOP initiative launched:

- To ensure the protection, advancement, and promotion of regional crafts and talents.
- To take ODOP products to national and international markets, also promote ODOP products using a disciplined strategy to a worldwide audience.
- To increase incomes/local employment, thus minimizing migration for jobs by raising wealth and creating more local jobs in the state
- To improve product quality and skill development
- To give assistance in key areas - technology, skill development, infrastructure, and finance
- To resolve issues of economic disparity and regional imbalance
- To boost overall exports of the chosen goods (Nayyar, 2021).

B. Four Pillars of ODO Initiative (ODOP Schemes):

Under the ODOP program UP government launched four schemes which comprise — Common Facility Centre Scheme (CFC), Marketing Development Assistance Scheme (MDA), Financial Assistance Scheme (Margin Money Scheme), and the Skill Development Scheme. The followings are the goals and operating principles of these schemes:

➤ Common Facility Centre Scheme (CFC):

The launch of the "Common Facility Key (CFC) Promotion Scheme" for the construction of facilities related to manufacturing, quality improvement, research and development, environment and energy conservation, packaging, etc., has the Governor's enthusiastic approval. Under the aforementioned constraints and limitations, common facilities will be built for the activities listed below about the district's identified products:

- Testing Lab;
- Design Development Learning Centre;
- Technology Research and Development;
- Product Demonstration Sales Centre;
- Raw Material Bank;
- Common Resource Centre;
- Common Production/Processing Centre;
- Common Logistics Centre;
- Information Collection, Analysis, and Dissemination Centre;
- Packaging, Labelling, and Barcoding Facilities;

Other infrastructural facilities connected to the value chain's "Missing Link" A Special Purpose Vehicle (SPV) that has been specifically established for this purpose will set up, run, and maintain the intended common facility. Self-help groups, cooperative societies, voluntary Organisations, producer companies, private limited companies, limited partnerships, etc., are all examples of SPVs that might take the shape of a Cape.

➤ Incentives under CFCs by State Government:

- For CFCs with project costs under Rs. 15 crores, the State government must contribute up to 90% of the project's total cost, with the SPV bearing the remaining 10%.
- Financial support would also be granted for CFCs with project costs that are greater than Rs 15 crore, provided that the State's participation is based on Rs 15 crore. only
- The State government can also approve capital for projects of a similar sort that have already received approval from the Central and State governments but are still unfinished due to a lack of funding. Such incomplete projects would be supported with the appropriate reason.
- With the Chief Minister's approval, any provision relating to the promotion plan for general facilities for the development of infrastructure facilities under the "One District One Product" program may be changed, deleted, or amended (ODOP UP).

➤ Marketing Development Assistance Scheme (MDA):

The marketing Development assistance scheme is to assist in promoting the market of products under the ODOP program. This plan aims to achieve equitable pricing for ODOP product exporters, entrepreneurs, weavers, and craftsmen. The program also allows for the onboarding of artisans on other e-commerce sites like Amazon and Flipkart. With the help of this program, participants in local, national, and international fairs and exhibitions can display and sell the products they've chosen for the ODOP project.

➤ Incentives under MDA by State Government:

For participating in local, national, and international fairs and exhibitions, a few initiatives are provided:

- 75 percent of the stall fee
- 75 percent of the transportation fee
- Ticket for travel on both sides
- Under this scheme, government encourage entrepreneurs to use technology and go for onboard use of e-commerce portal (Nayyar, 2021).

➤ Finance Assistance Scheme (Margin Money Scheme):

Following this plan, a portion of the project's cost will be provided to applicants as a subsidy to start the project. All nationalized banks, regional rural banks, and other scheduled banks will finance the program, and the departments of export promotion and micro, small, and medium enterprises will disburse the ODOP margin money subsidy in response to all filed applications (ODOP UP).

➤ Skill Development and Toolkit Distribution (SDTD) Scheme:

The goal of the ODOP Skill Development and Tool Kit Distribution Scheme is to meet the state of Uttar Pradesh's present and future need for a skilled labour force along the full value chain of ODOP products. The program also aims to arm the artisans and labourers through the delivery of appropriate modern tool kits (ODOP UP).

➤ Incentives under SDTD Scheme by State Government:

- A skilled artisan must receive the necessary training through RPL (Recognition of Prior Learning) and must be certified by the appropriate Sector Skill Councils (SSCs).
- Unskilled artisans must receive a 10-day training period. Following training, these artisans must receive RPL certification.
- During training, each trainee will get an honorarium of Rs. 200.
- The department shall offer skilled craftspeople a modern toolbox at no charge.
- To improve skill training, a memorandum of understanding (MOU) has been formed with the Quality Council of India (QCI), and Dr A.P.J. Abdul Kalam Technical University (AKTU) and IIT Kanpur are currently involved (Nayyar, 2021).

C. Implementation of ODOP initiative in Uttar Pradesh for Empowering local industries:

The state of Uttar Pradesh, in the centre of India, is home to sacred rivers, historic cities, and places of pilgrimage. With its network of motorways, industrial corridors, international airports, centres of excellence in education and medicine, and an exporter of indigenous goods, it is emerging in modern times as a driver of the country's economy (Government of Uttar Pradesh). Uttar Pradesh, which makes up 7.3% of all of India and spans an area of 2,40,928 square kilometers, is the fourth-largest state in terms of land area. With 19.98 crore people, or roughly 16.5% of the country's population, according to the 2011 census, it is also the most populous state (20180305_ODOP-English, n.d.). Of all the Indian states, Uttar Pradesh has the third-largest economy. In 2022–2023, this state's nominal GDP would be 24.39 lakh crores (\$310 billion). There are 44,495,063 urban residents in Uttar Pradesh (Economy of Uttar Pradesh). The government of Uttar Pradesh launched the One District One Product (ODOP) project to promote the domestic production of diverse handicrafts, ready-to-wear garments, leather goods, etc. District-by-district promotion of local and specialized products is the state government's goal. The programs have increased employment opportunities for numerous artisans and improved Uttar Pradesh's economy. This plan has been implemented by the Uttar Pradesh government in all 75 of the state's districts. In addition to receiving plaudits domestically, the program also enjoyed success abroad. Chief Minister Yogi Adityanath introduced the initiative in January 2018.

The novel ODOP experiment by CM Yogi is being addressed both domestically and internationally. The government has greatly aided the growth of traditional businesses and crafts. The state of Uttar Pradesh is well recognized for its wide variety of high-end goods, such as beautiful glassware, clothing decorated with chikankari and zari-zardozi, and wheat-stalk crafts. Unknown to the general public, such items are produced in the villages of UP. The ODOP program aims to promote these regionally unique goods and handicrafts so that the state's rich cultural heritage can be shown. The program strives to highlight the distinctive business or niche product of each district. Here are the identified products of each district of UP which is a part of the ODOP program. It shows the rich cultural heritage with unique skills and talent of the state;

- **Handloom and Textiles:** The handloom and textile industries in Uttar Pradesh have a long history. Under ODOP, goods, including carpets, rugs, chikankari embroidery, zardozi work, and Banarasi silk sarees, are promoted. These fields are well-known for the skill found in Varanasi, Lucknow, and Bhadohi.
- **Leather Products:** In addition to being the home of the Taj Mahal, Agra is a major centre for leather products. Under ODOP, goods, including leather accessories, bags, wallets, and shoes, are pushed. Modern designs are incorporated into traditional craftsmanship in this sector.
- **Brassware and Metal Handicrafts:** Moradabad, often known as the "Brass City," is well known for its metal

and brass handicrafts. Under ODOP, products, including kitchenware, ornamental accents, lamps, and furniture are promoted.

- **Furniture and Woodcraft:** Saharanpur is renowned for its furniture and woodcraft industries. It manufactures handicrafts, decorative objects, and furniture with beautiful carvings. To highlight the workmanship of the area, these products are supported by ODOP.
- **Agro-based Products:** Uttar Pradesh is an agricultural state, and the ODOP promotes several different agro-based products. This includes goods from places like Malihabad, where mangoes are grown; Agra, where potatoes are grown; Gorakhpur, where rice is grown; and Mathura, where traditional foods like Peda are produced.
- **Pottery and Terracotta:** The terracotta and pottery industries are well-known in Etawah and adjacent regions of Uttar Pradesh. To preserve the traditional art form, products, including clay pots, sculptures, and ornamental items, are marketed through ODOP.
- **Khadi & Handloom Clothes:** The ODOP promotes Khadi, the handwoven and handspun cloth. In many parts of Uttar Pradesh, sarees, kurtas, and accessories made of khadi are in high demand.
- Products made from herbs and the Ayurvedic philosophy are also encouraged by the government. Under ODOP, medicinal plants, herbs, and Ayurvedic drugs are prioritized; areas like Bareilly and Jhansi are renowned for their herbal products.

D. Export Expansion under ODOP:

In FY22, India's exports of goods reached a record \$420 billion. India's exports reached \$229 billion in H1FY23, and at this rate, they would surpass \$420 billion in the current fiscal year. With the introduction of a new logistics policy and the One District One Product - District Export Hub (ODOP-DEH) plan, the Government of India is on the right track to aiming for significant export growth. The ODOP-District Export Hub (DEH) is a pivotal step in realizing a district's full potential, igniting economic growth, creating jobs, and fostering rural entrepreneurship. Its goal is to promote balanced regional development across all of the country's districts, enabling holistic socio-economic growth throughout all regions and allowing MSMEs, farmers, and small businesses to benefit from export opportunities in foreign markets. Mangoes with GI tags were exported for the first time in June 2021. Malihabadi Dasherri mangoes were shipped from Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, to the UK, while GI-tagged Jardalu mangoes were exported for the first time from Bhagalpur, Bihar, to the UK. Although ODOP-DEH's emphasis on GI products is commendable, it might also concentrate more on maximizing the value of raw materials and intermediate products for integration into global value chains. Here are GI Products/Clusters identified for Export Promotion in Uttar Pradesh under ODOP- DEH: Agra Durrie, Hand Made Carpet, Khurja Pottery, Farrukhabad Prints, Firozabad Glass, Ghazipur Jute Wall hangings, Gorakhpur Terracota, Kalanamak Rice, Kannauj Perfume, Saddlery, Lucknow Chikan craft, Mango Malihabadi Dusseheri, Lucknow Zardozi, Meerut Scissors, Mirzapur Handmade Carpet, Moradabad Metal Craft, Saharanpur WoodCraft, Banaras Brocades, and Sarees,

Banaras Gulabi Meenakari Craft, Varanasi Wooden Lacquerware & Toys, Banaras Metal Repouse Craft, Varanasi Glass beads, Varanasi Soft Stone Jali Work. With the introduction of ODOP-DEH, exports have seen a tremendous increase in nearly all states (Research, 2022). Exports from Uttar Pradesh have increased more than thrice since the introduction of the ODOP-DEH initiative and shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Export of Uttar Pradesh (INR Th. Cr.)

Parameters	2016 -17	2017 -18	2019 -20	2020 -21	2021 -22
Share of UP in India's export	4.50 %	4.60 %	4.90 %	5.40 %	5.60 %
Export (INR Th. Cr.)	84	89	114	120	121

Source: (Niryat Patrika Uttar Pradesh Export Promotion Council, 2022)

Given that the Indian economy is service-based and that the service sector contributes roughly 55% of GDP, services exports should be given a higher priority under ODOP-DEH. However, the services that have been designated for export promotion are currently very few and only relate to tourism and IT/ITES. Services identified for Export Promotion under ODOP-DEH in the case of UP is religious tourism.

IV. FINDINGS AND OBSERVATION

With the help of a thorough study of the One District One Product (ODOP) Program, it can be said as proper implementation of the program can provide an edge as well as a tremendous positive change in Economic success, such as the increase in demand of Traditional Handicraft Products from within and outside India with the help of Branding. This can be reflected in

- *Increase in MSMEs in UP* (1st rank in the number of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSME) in India, 14.2 % of total)
- *Increase in Entrepreneurs* (By acquiring loans from the Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana, Stand Up, and Startup India, 5 lakh young people have started their businesses under the ODOP)
- *Increase in Export* (In the Top 5 exporting states of India, the following states contributed the most to exports in the fiscal year 2019 (18% year-over-year growth in exports): 4.8 %)
- *Increase In GDP of UP* (The third-largest economy in India, the State's GSDP increased by 10% over the last three years (2017–18 to 2019–20))
- *Improved Infrastructure* (Around 1120 miles of 8-lane expressways, 10,000 miles of railway network, 2 international airports, 5 domestic airports and 15 upcoming regional airports)
- *Wealthy Population of UP* (7% growth in Per capita income in last 3 years (2017-18 to 2019-20))
- *Trained and Qualified Youth* (Under the Vishwakarma Shram Samman Yojana, 5 lakh craftsmen get access to training and toolkits. 3.14 lakh enterprises have benefited

from ODOP and Vishwakarma Shram Samman's special initiative)

- 9 million MSME units have been developed, which is the second-highest number in India.
- 5 lakh young people have started businesses under the ODOP by receiving loans under the Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana, Stand Up, and Startup India programs.
- Around INR 89,000 Cr (USD 12.1 Bn) in exports in 2019–20
- Yogi Adityanath, the chief minister of Uttar Pradesh, laid the cornerstone for 13 Common Facility Centres throughout the state as part of the ODOP Program.
- Financial institutions provided MSMEs with roughly INR 57,000 Cr credit in FY 2018–19.
- Yogi Adityanath, the chief minister of Uttar Pradesh, transferred loans worth INR 2,447 Cr. online to 98,743 new Micro, Small, and Medium-Sized Enterprises (MSME) units in FY 2020–2113.
- An MOU was inked with the Bank of Baroda to launch the ODOPPSB59 online loan site (www.psbloansin59minutes.com/bob), which will make it simple for the industry to get financing. The portal features a specific area where ODOP producers, traders, and artists can apply for loans and receive approval in as little as 59 minutes.
- A memorandum of understanding was signed with the Small Industries Growth Bank of India (SIDBI), the main financial organization involved in the promotion, financing, and growth of the MSME ecosystem. Entrepreneurs will receive equity infusions, interest-rate rebates on loans, and other financial help under the arrangement with SIDBI. Sidbi will carry out a case-by-case analysis to encourage the export of OPOP goods.
- The units can obtain capital through the stock market thanks to MOUs with the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) and the National Stock Exchange of India Limited (NSE). Eight firms have listed thus yet, raising INR 103 Cr.
- Memorandums of Understanding with IIT Kanpur, IIT Varanasi, Dr A.P.J. Abdul Kalam Technical University (AKTU), IIIT Allahabad, IIP (Indian Institute of Packaging), Quality Council of India (QCI), National Institute of Fashion Technology (NIFT), and National Institute of Design (NID) would aid small units in developing new product designs, enhancing product quality, and developing inventive product packaging
- MOUs with eBay, Flipkart, and Amazon were signed.
- There are already 353 merchants on Amazon who have added close to 11,000 products.
- The UP Warehousing and Logistics Policy 2018 was introduced by the government of Uttar Pradesh to improve infrastructure to make exports practicable. The ODOP Branding Scheme, which is in the works, plans to brand and market ODOP products through stores at the block, tehsil, and district levels.

V. CONCLUSION

ODOP is a unique and highly successful initiative of the Government of Uttar Pradesh. In just two years, the success of the ODOP in Uttar Pradesh has inspired more than just other Indian states to undertake similar initiatives to revitalize local crafts and products at the National as well as global levels. This dream is now becoming a reality by identifying one product per district based on the potential and strengths of a district, as well as national priorities, and developing a cluster for that product in the district that is capable of producing a world-class product with quality, scalability, and a brand, and also create market linkages.

The state of Uttar Pradesh, in the centre of India, is home to sacred rivers, historic cities, and places of pilgrimage. The novel ODOP experiment by CM Yogi is being addressed both domestically and internationally. The government has greatly aided the growth of traditional businesses and crafts.

- Handloom and textiles: The handloom and textile industries in Uttar Pradesh have a long history. Under ODOP, goods, including carpets, rugs, chikankari embroidery, zardozi work, and Banarasi silk sarees are promoted.
- Leather products: Besides being the Taj Mahal's home, Agra is a major centre for leather products. Under ODOP, goods, including leather accessories, bags, wallets, and shoes, are pushed.
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- Khadi & Handloom Clothes: The ODOP promotes Khadi, the handwoven and handspun cloth.
- Products made from herbs and the Ayurvedic philosophy are also encouraged by the government.

In conclusion, India has witnessed a remarkable surge in its exports of goods in recent years, with FY22 attaining a record-breaking figure of \$420 billion. Furthermore, the first half of FY23 has already seen exports reach \$229 billion, setting a promising pace that is likely to surpass the previous fiscal year. This positive growth trajectory can be attributed to various factors, such as the implementation of a new logistics policy and the One Nation, One Market initiative. With these measures in place, India's export sector is poised to continue thriving, contributing to the country's economic expansion and global trade footprint.

By overcoming the weaknesses and strengthening the strengths with keeping in mind the threats, Authorities can grab the opportunity coming in the future. For this, successful planning and implantation are required from every responsible individual

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